

D4.1

Strategies for Improving Data Monetization (M24)

FIR

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Abstract

This document outlines strategies for improving data monetisation, building on a comprehensive literature review and analysis of existing industry practices. It presents a framework that identifies and categorises various monetisation strategies based on a structured questionnaire, providing tools to enhance accessibility to the strategy topic for the users of the platform. Among these tools are a 4x4 Pathway Matrix and a questionnaire designed to guide organisations in selecting appropriate monetisation approaches. These tools facilitate effective data utilisation, ultimately driving value creation and fostering a sustainable data economy. The framework serves as a practical guide for organisations seeking to optimise their data monetisation efforts in a rapidly evolving market.

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CL	Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	<input type="checkbox"/>
SEN	Confidential to DATAMITE project and Commission Services	<input type="checkbox"/>

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R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).
DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.
DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.
OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

AaaS	Answer-as-a-Service
AI	Artificial Intelligence
D4.1	Deliverable of task 4.1
DaaS	Data-as-a-Service
DoA	Description of Action
E2E	External to external
E2I	External to internal
EaaS	Equipment-as-a-Service
EDM	European Data Market Study
EU	European Union
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
I2E	Internal to external
I2I	Internal to internal
IaaS	Information-as-a-Service
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IDC	International Data Corporation
IoT	Internet of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M24	Month 24 of the project duration
R&D	Research and Development
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This document provides an overview of the DATAMITE project's focus on developing effective data monetisation strategies. It presents essential background information, identifies key concepts, and outlines specific strategies for enhancing the company's data monetisation practices.

The framework is based on an extensive literature review and an ecosystem analysis that examines stakeholders, value chains, value propositions, and revenue mechanisms associated with existing monetisation approaches. It categorises various strategies into distinct profiles, enabling organisations to navigate the complexities of data monetisation effectively.

The framework relies on two key tools: the 4x4 Pathway Matrix and a tailored questionnaire. The Pathway Matrix visually maps data flows, highlighting monetisation opportunities and risks, while the questionnaire assesses a business's strategic profile, capabilities, and challenges. Together, they provide a comprehensive approach, combining high-level pathway visualisation with detailed, personalised recommendations to guide effective data monetisation strategies.

This deliverable emphasises the importance of aligning data monetisation strategies with organisational objectives and market demands. By employing the provided tools, organisations can obtain tailored insights that facilitate informed decision-making and effective strategy implementation. The overarching aim of this deliverable is to drive value creation through optimised data utilisation, thereby contributing to a sustainable data economy.

To ensure the reliability and applicability of the proposed strategies, this deliverable emphasises the importance of evaluation and validation. While initial feedback was gathered through ecosystem analysis and pilot interviews, further validation will be conducted in subsequent tasks of the DATAMITE project. This includes the development of key performance indicators (KPIs) for assessing the effectiveness of data monetisation strategies and obtaining structured input from stakeholders to refine the framework. The validated results and insights will be documented in a publication to disseminate the findings and support broader adoption of the proposed strategies. These steps will ensure that the tools and approaches are both practical and aligned with the diverse needs of organisations.

In summary, this deliverable is a critical resource for organisations seeking to enhance their data monetisation efforts. It outlines the strategies and tools available while providing a foundational

understanding of the complexities involved in monetising data in the contemporary business landscape.

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1 Introduction

DATAMITE is a project funded by the European Commission as part of the Horizon Europe programme and coordinated by the ITI - Technological Institute of Informatics. DATAMITE empowers European companies by delivering a modular, open-source and multi-domain framework to improve DATA Monetising, Interoperability, Trading and Exchange, in the form of software modules, training, and business materials.

DATAMITE unleashes the monetisation potential at two levels. At internal level, users will have tools to improve quality management of their data, the adherence to FAIR principles, and will be able to upskill on technical and business aspects thanks to the multiple open-source training materials the project will generate. Therefore, data will become trustable and more reliable also in other paradigms like AI.

At an external level, keeping users in control of their data will provide new sources of revenue and interaction with other stakeholders. The architecture envisioned for DATAMITE enables DIHs sandboxing, becoming a potential instructor on their onboarding of SMEs and low-tech SMEs into the data economy. Together, DATAMITE's solutions will function as a catalyst to boost data monetisation in the European productive fabric.

1.1 Deliverable Purpose and Scope

Specifically, the Grant Agreement states the following regarding this Deliverable: *Provides the approach for developing data monetisation strategies and structures specific strategy profiles for data monetisation.*

Hence, the purpose of this deliverable, **D4.1 – Strategies for Improving Data Monetisation (M24)**, is to outline the approach for developing data monetisation strategies and corresponding strategy profiles. The deliverable focuses on two key objectives: **internal monetisation**, which involves optimising internal processes and reducing costs, and **external monetisation**, which entails creating and selling data-driven products and services.

To achieve these objectives, **Task 4.1** developed a framework of strategy profiles for monetising data in EU companies. This framework is grounded in an **ecosystem analysis** conducted across four distinct dimensions: stakeholders, value chain, value proposition, and revenue mechanisms for existing monetisation approaches. This approach aligns with Gassmann's Business Model Framework, particularly the "Magic Triangle," which focuses on the interplay between value

proposition, value creation, and revenue mechanisms to design effective business models. (Gassmann, Frankenberger, & Csik, 2013) In addition to the ecosystem analysis, interviews were conducted with pilots to gather insights regarding the requirements and the monetisation strategies they typically employ. Based on this analysis and the interview findings, target profiles of data monetisation strategies were derived and tailored to address the specific requirements, challenges, and opportunities identified for different types of stakeholders. The results were transformed into strategy profiles for improving monetisation, ensuring their flexibility and adaptability to various types of stakeholders. This adaptability is achieved by structuring the profiles around the four dimensions by Gassmann and structuring the results using the Value Proposition Canvas by Osterwalder et al. (2014), which are relevant across industries and organisational contexts. Furthermore, the modular nature of the strategy profiles allows them to be extended or adapted to other strategies beyond those initially considered, providing a robust foundation for broader application in diverse scenarios. The report outlines the approach for developing data monetisation strategies and structures specific strategy profiles for data monetisation. To ensure our findings are accessible to external users, we developed practical tools to facilitate the application of the framework. We developed a questionnaire to help DATAMITE users identify the most suitable data monetisation strategy and receive tailored recommendations. The goal is to integrate this tool into the DATAMITE platform for seamless accessibility. Overall, this work in Task 4.1 is crucial for further tasks in Work Package (WP) 4 and serves as an initial step for users in establishing a business model. Later tasks in WP4 will refer to the work done in Task 4.1 and will elaborate on these profiles, going into more detail concerning the value of datasets, models for Data Sharing Platforms, and social aspects like legal and ethical perspectives.

1.2 Document Structure

This deliverable is broken down into the following sections:

- **Executive Summary:** A summary of the contents and main findings are provided.
- **Section 1 – Introduction:** Provides the deliverable's general context, dependencies, and structure.
- **Section 2 – Background:** Provides key background information on data monetisation, market trends, and industry insights, highlighting challenges and opportunities.

- **Section 3 – Understanding Data Monetisation:** Outlines key concepts and types of data monetisation, including direct and indirect approaches, while reviewing value propositions, current practices, and industry benchmarks.
- **Section 4 – Strategies for improving data monetisation:** Details strategies to enhance data monetisation, focusing on analytics, data products, and services, with profiles based on the Data Monetisation Framework.
- **Section 5 – Conclusion:** Summarizing the key points of this deliverable.

Appendices:

- **Appendix A:** Guidelines of the Monetisation Framework provides guidelines for using the Data Monetisation Framework's tools.
- **Appendix B:** Strategy Questionnaire Responses. This includes tables with the answers to the questionnaire for each of the identified data monetisation strategies.

2 Background

It is key to understand the current background the data economy is facing. For this, a thorough ecosystem review has been conducted, giving insights concerning the situation of companies seeking to improve their work with data.

2.1 Industry Trends and Market Overview

The growth in global data production is evident. It increased from 33 zettabytes in 2018 to a projected 175 zettabytes by 2025. Digital data are exchanged as products or services and increase the value of the data marketplaces. In 2021, Europe's data market value was 63.8 billion, a 4.9% increase over the observed in 2020. However, it is expected to peak growth in 2030, with an increase of 6.8% between 2025 and 2030, from around 90 to 125 billion euros (European Commission, 2022).

This increase in data production and data trading presents the chance for the European Union (EU) to assert its global leadership in the scope of creating opportunities on paradigms such as data storage, data processing, data heterogeneity or benefits on their exploitation.

Now, approximately 80% of data processing and analytical functions are developed within centralised data centres, while the remaining 20% is distributed across smart connected entities, encompassing vehicular platforms, domestic appliances, manufacturing automation, and proximal user-centric computing facilities – referred to as 'edge computing' (European Commission, 2020). This prospective realignment not only underscores economic and sustainable advantages but also offers novel prospects for enterprises to devise tools that facilitate data producers in enhancing their control over proprietary data.

The significance and growth of the European data market also became evident during the pandemic. The COVID-19 pandemic significantly impacted the European economy, causing a 5.6% contraction in the EU's gross domestic product (GDP) in 2020, the largest economic downturn in EU history since the 2007-2008 financial crisis. Despite this, the EU showed resilience by rebounding to pre-pandemic GDP levels within a year of the lockdowns ending. Especially the European IT market, highlighted in the European Data Market Study (EDM), demonstrated adaptability, with the International Data Corporation (IDC) projecting market values of 584 billion euros in 2020, increasing to 624 billion euros in 2021, and anticipating a further 3% increase in 2022 (European Commission, 2022). Meanwhile, the pandemic affected the labour

market differently, with a significant decrease in the active workforce in 2020, recovering slowly into 2021. However, the number of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) employed specialists in the EU not only withstood the uncertainties but also accelerated growth during this period, underscoring the sector's resilience and importance in the digital-first economy.

Overall, the ecosystem analysis identifies five categories of organisations that can benefit from the DATAMITE platform. These categories were derived through a structured market analysis, which examined the European data ecosystem, focusing on the roles and functions of various stakeholders. The analysis considered key aspects of the data value chain, including data generation, processing, dissemination, and utilisation. By mapping organisations to their specific contributions within this ecosystem, the following five categories emerged:

1. **Core Organisations:** Include data providers, data analytics companies, data science labs, government agencies, and nonprofit organisations focusing on various data-driven activities.
2. **Supporting Organisations:** Encompass Data Integration Service Providers, Data Visualization Studios, Data Governance Consultants, Data Storage and Infrastructure Providers, and Data Security Firms, all supporting data management and security.
3. **Distribution Channels:** Consist of Data Marketplaces, Data as a Service (DaaS) Providers, Data Publishers, and Data Aggregators facilitating the exchange and dissemination of data.
4. **Regulatory and Policy Entities:** Comprise Data Protection Agencies, Data Ethics Committees, and Standards Bodies ensuring compliance and ethical use of data.
5. **Research and Development:** Include Data Science Research Institutions, Innovation Hubs, and Technology Providers advancing data science through research, innovation, and technology solutions.

These categories highlight the diverse stakeholders involved in leveraging data for various purposes within the DATAMITE ecosystem.

2.2 Challenges and Opportunities

In the interconnected world of today's digital landscape, data has emerged as a transformative asset driving innovation, efficiency, and competitive advantage across industries. Nowhere is this more evident than in the European Data Ecosystem, a vibrant tapestry of organisations spanning diverse sectors. At the core of this ecosystem lie data platforms and pivotal infrastructures

designed to collect, analyse, and harness data for strategic insights and operational enhancements.

Seizing Opportunities

The implementation of data platforms presents a myriad of opportunities for organisations operating within the European market. First and foremost, data monetisation stands as a cornerstone for revenue generation, enabling businesses to capitalise on their data assets by selling insights to third parties for ecosystem analysis, customer segmentation, and targeted advertising (Parvinen, Pöyry, Gustafsson, Laitila, & Rossi, 2020). Moreover, the ability to leverage data-driven insights facilitates improved decision-making processes, empowering businesses to optimise operations and respond swiftly to market trends. Enhanced customer experiences further underscore the potential of data platforms, allowing organisations to tailor products and services to individual preferences and behaviours (Onesi-Ozigagun, Ololade, Eyo-Udo, & Ogundipe, 2024).

Navigating Challenges

Despite the opportunities presented by data monetisation, significant challenges must be addressed to fully unlock its potential.

Regulatory complexities pose a major hurdle, exemplified by the stringent General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and similar data protection frameworks. These regulations impose rigorous requirements on data handling practices, making compliance a challenging but necessary endeavour. Organisations must implement meticulous compliance strategies and establish robust governance frameworks to navigate legal uncertainties while ensuring the privacy and security of personal data (Ruohonen & Mickelsson, 2023).

Technical obstacles also present formidable barriers to successful data monetisation. Data security remains a top concern, as protecting sensitive information from breaches and unauthorised access is critical to maintaining trust and legal compliance (Smith, Dinev, & Xu, 2011). In addition, ensuring data quality assurance—such as accuracy, consistency, and reliability—requires comprehensive validation processes and ongoing monitoring to make datasets usable and valuable (Faroukhi, Alaoui, Gahi, & Amine, 2020).

Another challenge lies in data integration across diverse systems. Many organisations operate with siloed data, legacy systems, and incompatible platforms, which hinder the seamless flow and analysis of data. Overcoming these barriers requires harmonization and the adoption of interoperable technologies that can unify disparate data sources (Linthicum, 1999).

Furthermore, scalability is a pressing issue as data volumes grow exponentially. Building infrastructure that can handle increasing data demands without incurring excessive costs is essential for operational efficiency and future growth (Gandomi & Haider, 2015).

Lastly, interoperability remains a key challenge, as data must flow seamlessly across various tools, platforms, and systems. Open standards, APIs, and well-defined architectures are necessary to ensure that organisations can exchange, process, and analyse data effectively within the broader ecosystem (Linthicum, 1999).

Lastly, interoperability remains a key challenge, as data must flow seamlessly across various tools, platforms, and systems. Open standards, APIs, and well-defined architectures are necessary to ensure that organisations can exchange, process, and analyse data effectively within the broader ecosystem.

Addressing these challenges requires substantial investments in infrastructure, expertise, and technology to safeguard data integrity, optimise operational processes, and achieve compliance with evolving regulatory requirements.

Beyond Technicalities

Beyond technical and regulatory hurdles, social and cultural factors play pivotal roles in shaping the adoption of data platforms. Varying attitudes towards data privacy, ownership, and sharing practices across different cultures underscore the need for nuanced approaches to foster trust and acceptance within diverse societal contexts (Alsaleh, Elliott, Fu, & Thakur, 2019). Economic and financial considerations further underscore the complexities of implementing data platforms, with costs associated with infrastructure, maintenance, and aligning economic incentives for data sharing posing potential barriers to adoption and scalability (Gandomi & Haider, 2015).

Organisations also face significant challenges in defining profitable data monetisation strategies. Without established guidelines, pricing strategies, revenue models, and value propositions become ambiguous, misaligning monetisation efforts with business objectives and resulting in missed revenue opportunities. The lack of standardized practices affects trust and transparency in data transactions, discouraging potential partners. Moreover, data providers often struggle to balance revenue maximization with the costs of data acquisition, complicated by the challenge of assessing potential returns and the uncertain nature of data asset monetisation (Firouzi, Farahani, Barzegari, & Daneshmand, 2022).

A Roadmap to Success

Successfully navigating these challenges while capitalising on opportunities is crucial for organisations seeking to establish and sustain data platforms within the European Data Ecosystem. By understanding the intricacies of regulatory compliance, technical readiness, societal acceptance, and economic viability, businesses can forge pathways towards innovation, compliance, and competitive advantage in the digital age.

In the following sections, we delve deeper into these dynamics, exploring the specific opportunities that data platforms present, the formidable barriers they encounter, and strategies for overcoming these challenges to realise the full potential of data-driven strategies in Europe's dynamic business landscape.

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3 Understanding Data Monetisation

Section 3 goes into detail concerning the concept of Data Monetisation. This overview is needed because it is a key aspect of the overall DATAMITE project and because of the need for a consistent definition for future tasks in this WP. Beginning with a general definition of key concepts and continuing with the introduction of the two key forms of Data Monetisation in 3.2., that is going to be elaborated in more detail in Section 4. Furthermore, Sections 3.3 and 3.4 explore Data Monetisation in the important categories of “Value Proposition”, “Stakeholder”, “Value creation”, and “Revenue mechanisms”, laying the foundation for understanding this Task and especially for preparing the frame that WP4 will work in.

3.1 Definition and Key Concepts

The concept of data monetisation involves leveraging organisational data to generate revenue, either through direct sales or by creating value indirectly. Although data monetisation is not a novel idea, the advent of Big Data and the Big Data Value Chain has significantly increased its appeal (Faroukhi, Alaoui, Gahi, & Amine, 2020). More concretely, the rapid digitalisation of the global economy has transformed data into a valuable, strategic asset with the potential to drive innovation, enhance productivity, and unlock new revenue streams for businesses and governments alike. This shift has been particularly pronounced in Europe, where the rise of data-driven business models, the proliferation of digital platforms, and the increasing importance of data-centric technologies have all contributed to the emergence of a thriving data economy. However, data monetisation in Europe has not been without its challenges. Concerns over data privacy, security, and sovereignty have led to the development of a comprehensive regulatory framework, including the GDPR and the proposed Data Governance Act and Data Act, which aim to strike a balance between unlocking the economic potential of data and safeguarding the rights and interests of individuals and organisations (Ruohonen & Mickelsson, 2023). Moreover, the fragmentation of data assets across organisational and national boundaries, as well as the lack of interoperability between data management systems, has hindered the ability of European businesses and public entities to fully capitalise on the value of their data.

In response to these challenges, the European Union has made data monetisation a key priority within its broader digital agenda, articulated in the European Data Strategy (Correnti, 2024). This ambitious initiative seeks to create a unified, ethical, and secure data ecosystem that empowers

European citizens and businesses to derive maximum value from their data assets while ensuring that the benefits of the data economy are distributed equitably across the continent.

Monetisation of data is of growing importance since data is one of the most valuable resources in the world, and it is a critical issue that many industries face today (Wixom, 2014).

The data monetisation global market is projected to exhibit substantial growth based on a study by Kanhaiya et al. (2022) the market is estimated to grow from \$2.1 billion in 2020 to \$15.5 billion in 2030. This expansion is underpinned by several driving factors: the increasing magnitude of generated data, awareness of data monetisation, and emerging technology opportunities and trends (Baecker, Engert, Pfaff, & Krcmar, 2020, S. 1; Moore, 2015). Further driving factors are the technologies beyond these trends, such as Business Intelligence and Analytics, cloud computing, blockchain, Internet of Things (IoT), social networks and post-COVID-19 pandemic business approaches and strategies (Parvinen, Pöyry, Gustafsson, Laitila, & Rossi, 2020; MordorIntelligence, 2022).

Unlocking hidden value within an organisation's data is a strategic move with immense potential. As noted by Constantiou and Kallinikos (2015), monetising data taps into a valuable but often underutilised asset. It can generate revenue, serving as an additional income stream for an organisation, especially if the core business model has limitations or there is a need for diversification. Data monetisation provides customised insights to clients, offering industry-specific information to make informed decisions and stay competitive. This sets an organisation apart by offering high-quality data that may be more comprehensive, accurate, or timely than competitors (Faroukhi, Alaoui, Gahi, & Amine, 2020). Moreover, as highlighted by McAfee and Brynjolfsson (2012), data mitigates risks by enabling informed decisions in financial, operational, and strategic aspects, fostering a secure business environment. Businesses purchasing data, as reported in the research by Chen et al. (2012), can save costs by relying on the expertise and infrastructure provided. Scalability is a key feature where growing data assets expand the potential audience and diversity of datasets (Gandomi & Haider, 2015). However, it's crucial to build the strategy on a foundation of compliance and security, ensuring alignment with data protection regulations (Smith, Dinev, & Xu, 2011). Hartmann et al. (2016) also highlight that offering flexible data products and packages caters to diverse client needs and budgets, including raw data, real-time feeds, and data analytics services. Overall, building long-term partnerships with clients relying on the data is a testament to the value it brings, fostering repeat business and referrals (Palmatier, Dant, Grewal, & Evans, 2006).

For organisations aspiring to craft a successful data monetisation strategy, an indispensable prerequisite is a profound comprehension of their unique use case (Parvinen, Pöyry, Gustafsson, Laitila, & Rossi, 2020). This necessitates an exhaustive examination of their value proposition, characterised by an intensive deliberation of their distinct operational context.

For this reason, the following sections discuss various theoretical approaches, revenue models, offerings and products as well as customer segments from the literature and the pilots conducted.

3.2 Types of Data Monetisation

The two main approaches to monetising data that offer different strategies for realising the financial potential of data assets are explained in the following sections: direct and indirect (Wixom & Ross, 2017; Zhang, Yue, Yu, & Zhang, 2022; Parvinen, Pöyry, Gustafsson, Laitila, & Rossi, 2020; Ofulue & Benyoucef, 2022; Moore, 2015). It is important to keep this distinction to get a better understanding of possible problems and opportunities that can occur during the implementation of a Monetisation Concept.

3.2.1 Direct Monetisation

Direct data monetisation involves generating revenue by selling data as a product or service (Zhang, Yue, Yu, & Zhang, 2022). In this approach, companies treat data as a valuable asset that can be directly exchanged for monetary gain. For instance, organisations can sell their raw data to other businesses or individuals. This data may encompass a wide range of information, such as customer data, ecosystem research findings, or sensor data (Parvinen, Pöyry, Gustafsson, Laitila, & Rossi, 2020). In addition, there are other approaches, such as bartering or wrapping the data (Wixom, 2014). Bartering can be an attractive opportunity because companies can acquire new tools, services, or special deals in exchange for their raw data with third parties such as suppliers (Wixom, 2014; Baecker, Engert, Pfaff, & Krcmar, 2020). Wrapping refers to the practice where companies create a positive financial impact by packaging “free” information products and services with core offerings. The intended results of wrapping include higher market and wallet share, a larger share of customers' spending, increased customer loyalty, switching costs, and prices (Wixom, 2014). Additionally, organisations have the option to market and sell information or knowledge that results from any stage of the insights generation process, including analytics, visualisation, and other data processing steps (Baecker, Engert, Pfaff, & Krcmar, 2020).

3.2.2 Indirect Monetisation

Indirect data monetisation focuses on using data to enhance existing products, services, or operations, ultimately leading to increased revenue through improved offerings or business processes (Wixom & Ross, 2017). Instead of selling data directly, companies wrap data to provide added value. For instance, analysing customer data can lead to personalised recommendations or product optimisations, potentially boosting sales and customer satisfaction (Porter & Heppelmann, 2015). Data-driven insights enable companies to serve targeted advertisements and provide advertising partners access to specific demographics or audiences, resulting in advertising revenue (Parvinen, Pöyry, Gustafsson, Laitila, & Rossi, 2020). Furthermore, data is used in research and development to identify innovative products, services, or business opportunities (Sorescu, 2017).

The choice between these approaches depends on various aspects: the type of data, competitive factors, the products and the strategic goals of the business (Parvinen, Pöyry, Gustafsson, Laitila, & Rossi, 2020). A combination of both approaches is also possible and purposeful to maximise the value of the data assets (Wixom & Ross, 2017; Thomas & Leiponen, 2016).

3.3 Value Proposition of Data Monetisation and Stakeholder

In data-driven business models, value proposition and stakeholder engagement are critical (Freudenreich, Lüdeke-Freund, & Schaltegger, 2020). These models leverage data insights to create and deliver value to customers, aligning products and services with customer needs while effectively managing stakeholder relationships. Subscription business models guarantee specific outcomes for customers, such as increased productivity. This model shifts the risk from the customer to the provider, ensuring that customers benefit from the successful use of a solution package. Key elements such as Process, Product & Service, and Pain & Gain are essential in crafting value propositions within these models.

The integration of products and services is central to data-driven business models, ensuring a holistic customer experience. By utilising data insights, businesses can tailor their offerings to meet customer needs, fostering adaptability and innovation. This approach exemplifies indirect monetisation, where data is used to enhance existing products, services, and customer experiences rather than being sold directly. Indirect monetisation focuses on creating added value through operational improvements, customer-centric solutions, and innovation-driven strategies. For instance, a leading European bank increased sales by 12% through personalised website

content based on customer data and predicted needs (Bilbao-Osorio, Dutta, & Lanvin, 2014). Data-driven insights enable businesses to refine their processes, anticipate customer needs, and enhance operational efficiency. Process optimisation involves integrating resources and procedures to create competitive advantages. However, a robust infrastructure is essential for the effective use of data. This includes ensuring data quality, security, and compliance, as well as facilitating swift data processing and analysis. A well-developed infrastructure supports enhanced customer relationships and promotes continuous improvement, aligning with organisational goals and the dynamic nature of data-driven strategies.

As previously mentioned, the Value Proposition Canvas by Osterwalder et al. (2014) was employed as a method to structure the framework's development. It illustrates how different processes can be established based on the products and services offered, improving the relationship between customers and providers. Businesses must focus on addressing customer pains and creating gains. Pain Relievers eliminate obstacles that hinder customers, while Gain Creators highlight the benefits provided by a business's products and services. This dual approach ensures that businesses effectively meet customer needs and enhance their overall experience. Customised value propositions are vital for different stakeholders. The Value Proposition Canvas helps create customer-centric propositions by systematically addressing the demands and challenges of prospective data consumers. This approach aids in risk mitigation, fosters innovation, and optimises resource allocation (Osterwalder, Pigneur, Bernarda, & Smith, 2014). For data providers and consumers, value propositions focus on the commerce of raw data. Data providers benefit from new revenue channels, while consumers gain access to new markets and synergies. Effective data exchange enhances company performance by fostering cooperation and providing diverse data sources.

Data prosumers engage in both selling and internally using data. Each activity must be treated as a discrete case, with tailored value propositions for each role. This dual approach allows prosumers to maximise the benefits of their data activities. In consulting, value propositions include offering expertise and training to enhance resource management flexibility and provide rapid support. Challenges such as customization difficulties and data privacy concerns must be proactively addressed. Marketplaces for data monetisation offer benefits like secure payment systems and analytics tools. However, concerns about data security and vendor reliability must be managed to ensure successful stakeholder engagement.

In data-driven business models, creating value propositions and engaging stakeholders effectively are crucial. By integrating products and services, optimising processes, addressing customer pains and gains, and developing a robust infrastructure, businesses can maximize the benefits of data monetisation. Customized value propositions for different stakeholders, including data providers, consumers, prosumers, and consultants, ensure that businesses can meet diverse needs and enhance overall customer experience.

3.4 Value Creation Chain and Revenue Mechanisms

Baeker et al. (2020) define data value creation as the process of translating the potential value inherent in data into tangible benefits. This process is rooted in the data–information–knowledge hierarchy, where data represent raw facts and observations without inherent meaning, and information is the result of analysing and interpreting data. Within the data value chain, data serve as fundamental raw materials, with information emerging through subsequent analytical processes. Eggert et al. (2018) discuss the distinction between "value-in-exchange" and "value-in-use." This categorisation can be applied to the context of data value, where value creation arises not only from the modification of raw data but also from the transformation of data into meaningful information. Both activities require resources but yield substantial value in return.

Building on this foundational understanding, Kakuschke (2024) expands the concept of data value creation to encompass the development of products and services derived from data and the utilisation of data to enhance existing organisational functions. Through a thorough literature review, Kakuschke (2024) categorises organisational data value creation into 12 distinct options. Using a two-dimensional classification scheme where "data" and "information" form one axis and "own use" versus "exchange" form the other. These options include:

- Increasing the value of an organisation's data assets through data preparation.
- Enhancing the value of an organisation's information assets by creating new insights.
- Optimising or innovating products and services based on data-driven insights.
- Fine-tuning pricing strategies through data analytics.
- Improving customer interaction and company perception using data-driven approaches.
- Streamlining organisational processes through data-driven optimisation.
- Exchanging raw data with external entities.
- Exchanging prepared data in any modified form to meet specific needs.
- Sharing insights derived from data analysis with external stakeholders.

- Exchanging data models or components used in analytical processes.
- Wrapping core products or services with additional information derived from data.
- Delivering services grounded in information to take proactive actions for customers.

These categories illustrate the breadth of opportunities for organisations to create and extract value from data. They underscore the dual importance of leveraging data for internal improvement and strategic external exchange, highlighting data-driven approaches as critical drivers of business innovation and competitiveness in today's digital economy.

Knowing the value that can be extracted from data is a crucial step towards an efficient pricing method that is suitable and flexible enough to encompass various forms of Data and Data Products. This topic of Data Pricing is part of the following Task in WP4. Nevertheless, the strategy of revenue generation can still be elaborated without the pricing component.

In the examination of revenue mechanisms within data-driven business models, several fundamental aspects align closely with the 12 strategies for data value creation outlined by Kakuschke (2024). These aspects form a foundational framework for understanding how organisations generate income and value through their data-driven services: Revenue Models, Decision-Making Processes, Monetisation, Value Capture, Customer-Specific Value Perception, and Costs & Risks. These components are pivotal as they outline how organisations generate income through their data-driven services.

Decision-Making Processes play a crucial role in elucidating companies select specific revenue models in the dynamic data-driven landscape. Whether influenced by rational choice theory or organisational objectives, understanding decision-making processes enhances insights into motivations, patterns, and the factors driving the adoption of distinct revenue mechanisms. This understanding empowers businesses to refine strategies that are finely tuned to their overarching goals, promoting sustainable success.

Monetisation Goals are central to revenue mechanisms as they aim to align chosen models with a company's specific objectives. Strategies such as selling data, bartering, or integrating it with products and services are meticulously examined to ensure they meet financial targets effectively. This alignment is vital for both internal operations and external engagements in data monetisation.

Costs and Risks Evaluation is essential in revenue mechanisms, encompassing the financial implications associated with implementing and operating these models. It includes upfront costs like infrastructure development, technology acquisition, and data security management, as well as ongoing operational expenses. Furthermore, it addresses risks related to regulatory

compliance, data security, and market uncertainties. This aspect is closely tied to strategic decision-making, enabling businesses to anticipate, mitigate, and manage costs and risks effectively.

Customer-Specific Value Perception holds significant importance in tailoring strategies across diverse sectors. Understanding how different customer segments perceive value based on their unique characteristics and preferences is key. By recognizing the diversity among customers, organisations can customize their approaches to meet the specific needs and challenges of various industries. This approach involves identifying both commonalities and distinctions in revenue mechanisms across different sectors, thereby facilitating the development of broad strategies and targeted, sector-specific solutions. Ultimately, this customer-centric and sector-specific approach optimises the effectiveness of strategies and solutions across a wide range of contexts.

Revenue Models encompass a variety of strategies employed by businesses to derive value from their data:

Direct revenue models, as part of data monetisation strategies, include asset sales (e.g., selling raw data), licensing intellectual property, and temporary asset use (e.g., renting). Subscription models provide stable income streams through tiered plans, requiring alignment with customer satisfaction and value propositions for sustained success. The multi-sided revenue model involves two interdependent revenue streams facilitated by data exchange between upstream and downstream customers, leveraging this interdependence to enhance overall value.

These models are classified and detailed in Table 1, providing insights into their applications and distinctions within different operational contexts. Understanding these revenue mechanisms enables businesses to effectively harness their data resources and optimise revenue generation strategies tailored to their specific industry environments.

Direct Revenue Models	
Asset sale, direct selling	Giving away the ownership rights of a good or service in exchange for money. An example of this is selling raw data (Kühne & Böhm, 2018).
Licensing	An organisation grants permission to use protected intellectual property like a patent or copyright in exchange for a licensing fee (Hartmann, Zaki, Feldmann, & Neely, 2016).
Lending, Renting, and Leasing	Temporarily grants someone the exclusive right to use an asset for a defined period (Hartmann, Zaki, Feldmann, & Neely, 2016).
Subscription Models	
Availability-based model (pay-per-availability)	The availability-based describes a subscription model where customers are charged a predetermined service fee for a specific duration, irrespective of the extent to which they utilise the offering within that timeframe. The pricing

	structure ensures accessibility throughout the designated period, providing users with flexibility while maintaining a consistent revenue stream for the service provider.
Pay-per-outcome	Customers are charged based on the results or outcomes they achieve through a product or service rather than a flat fee or ongoing subscription. In this model, the cost is directly tied to the success or value derived from the use of the product or service. This approach aligns the interests of the provider and the customer, as the customer pays for tangible and measurable results. It is commonly used in various industries, including marketing, consulting, and software services, where the value delivered can be clearly defined and quantified (Frank, Holst, Müller, & Leiting, 2021).
Profit sharing (pay-per-economic-success)	The profit-sharing revenue mechanism, a subset of the subscription model, compensates services based on the value generated for the customer. This model aligns with customer satisfaction, fostering innovation, but challenges include measuring value accurately and establishing transparent profit-sharing arrangements. Implementation requires a robust system for evaluating customer value and presenting potential technological and organisational challenges (Schüritz, Seebacher, & Dorner, 2017).
Pay-per-use	The pay-per-use revenue mechanism, a variant of the subscription model, charges customers based on service usage intensity, offering flexibility but with the challenge of potentially increased costs for intensive users. While advantageous for diverse customer needs, finding a balance between flexibility and cost alignment is crucial for providers, necessitating careful design and communication of pricing structures (Frank, Holst, Müller, & Leiting, 2021).
Multi-sided Revenue Models	
Endure-Ads	The Endure-Ads revenue mechanism offers free service access with personalised ads, creating a potential win-win. While providing cost-free access to users and benefiting advertisers with targeted ads, the challenge lies in maintaining a positive user experience and avoiding dissatisfaction caused by intrusive ads. Striking the right balance is crucial, requiring effective data analytics to ensure ads align with user preferences (Schüritz, Seebacher, & Dorner, 2017).
Data-tailored offering	In a data-tailored-offering setup, downstream customers share some private data with a service provider, who then connects them with upstream customers. Upstream customers pay for access to this data either through a subscription or usage fee, and the service provider may charge a brokerage fee for extra revenue. There is a direct interaction between upstream and downstream customers on the service provider's platform (Schüritz, Seebacher, & Dorner, 2017).
Buy-and-sell-data	In this model, the service provider acts as a data broker, connecting downstream customers who want to sell their data to potential buyers. Revenue is generated through profit-sharing arrangements between the service provider and downstream customers. There is no direct interaction between upstream and downstream customers; the service provider acts as an intermediary (Schüritz, Seebacher, & Dorner, 2017).
Pay-with-data	In the pay-with-data model, downstream customers use a data-driven service and share personal data in exchange for access to various services. This data is then offered to upstream customers who pay a subscription or usage fee. There's no direct interaction between upstream and downstream customers in this model (Schüritz, Seebacher, & Dorner, 2017).

Table 1: Description of different revenue models

4 Strategies for Improving Data Monetisation

In this chapter, different strategies will be depicted and explained using the tools provided by the strategy framework. Those tools include a 4x4 pathway matrix and a questionnaire, which will be explained in Sections 4.2.1 and 4.2.2 respectively. The pathway through the table is determined by the responses provided by DATAMITE users in the questionnaire. This pathway can then be aligned with the various monetisation strategies, allowing us to recommend the most suitable strategy based on their answers. The different strategies are explained and linked to the tools in Section 4.2.3. The goal is to elaborate on these different strategies to find similarities and to be able to group them into categories for our further work concerning the broader context of WP4. This will also be a first step into understanding the DATAMITE users and providing them with the right tools and materials based on the strategy they want to pursue.

Please note that results for one distinct strategy may vary according to different answers given in the questionnaire and it is possible to pursue a combination of strategies. These will get less damaging to this process as we proceed in WP4 work, due to a more detailed differentiation in terms of KPIs and a maturity model. We understand these strategies as “building blocks” for an efficient monetisation approach. Section 4.1 will focus on the importance of creating a Data-Driven Offering and what categories of offerings can be proposed by a company. After that, Section 4.2 will go into more detail, showing the Task’s result in a comprehensive overview.

4.1 Creating New Data-Driven Offerings

Key to enabling a strong data monetisation strategy is elaborating on the presented value proposition, revenue mechanisms, value creation chain and stakeholder. Keeping in mind that pricing models and billing are part of tasks T4.2 and T4.3, D4.1 focuses on the foundation of strategy profiles concerning the optimisation of internal processes and reduction of costs (internal monetisation) and external selling of data products and services (external monetisation). External monetisation can be achieved through various forms involving increasing data-product complexity. Direct data monetisation focuses on the data itself and the information that can be derived from it. Data-as-a-Service starts with selling raw data but can be developed to - or accompanied by – thorough analysis and reports, transforming it into an Information-as-a-Service approach. Building on top of this, Answers-as-a-Service not only provides an analysis but also possibilities for interpreting these, thus enabling more specific solutions like consulting and support services. The indirect form of external data monetisation is tied to already existing

products or services enhancing their quality and capabilities. In addition to that, monetisation strategies like “data bartering” and “share for free” can be crucial to a company’s general strategy by driving traffic or collecting consumer data in exchange for a “free” product or service. These two strategies need to be specifically tailored to a customer’s business and environment.

4.2 Monetisation Strategies

To provide a comprehensive understanding of the monetisation strategies, their foundation and definition must first be clarified. These strategies are derived from the 12 distinct options for data value creation identified in prior analysis. Approaches such as the exchange of raw data, the sharing of insights, the augmentation of core products with additional information, and the delivery of proactive services were established as fundamental pathways for data monetisation.

Within this framework, a distinction is made between internal monetisation, which focuses on the optimisation of internal processes and cost efficiency, and external monetisation, where value is created through the exchange, licensing, or sale of data products and services. This categorisation ensures a systematic approach to value capture both internally and externally.

To facilitate the identification and visualization of applicable monetisation strategies, a 4x4 matrix and an accompanying questionnaire have been developed. These tools are designed to assess a DATAMITE user’s current situation or their desired future state. Through their application, the strategies, which are rooted in the 12 options for data value creation, are analysed and aligned with the user’s specific goals.

Due to the modular nature of the core DATAMITE product, an individual assessment of the user’s situation is required to recommend suitable tools or solutions. Guidelines for the matrix and questionnaire have been provided (Appendix A: Guidelines of the Monetisation Framework) to ensure consistent and effective application. These guidelines serve as the foundation for implementing the findings from Task 4.1 in practice. Furthermore, the practical application of these tools informs other DATAMITE tasks and contributes relevant input to the development of KPIs and business blueprints.

4.2.1 Monetisation Pathway Matrix

The first model consists of a 4x4 matrix and is called the “pathway-matrix” accordingly. This model is intended to provide an overview of the current status of the company’s data monetisation strategy. The literature review revealed that both internal and external factors need to be considered to successfully monetize one’s data. It is also important to track where the data comes

from, what happens to it, where it is ultimately used and how revenue can be generated. As all these factors are interlinked and cannot be viewed in isolation, it is beneficial to present them in a matrix. This model can be widely applied to various organisations to assess their data monetisation strategies. However, there may be exceptions and specific circumstances that are not fully addressed by this model. The authors do not claim absolute applicability or completeness for all possible scenarios.

The matrix can be derived from the Gassmann business model. This model comprises four dimensions: Revenue model, value proposition, value creation process and target customer (Gassmann, Frankenberger, & Csik, 2013). Further information on this can be found in Section 3.4. Data monetisation places particular emphasis on interaction with the target customer: The aim is to process, market and sell the (own) data. If you rearrange the dimensions, with the target customer dimension still in the foreground, you get a matrix as shown in Figure 1. In the matrix, the “Target Customer” dimension is retained as the central focus and arranged vertically, representing the primary perspective for data monetisation efforts. The remaining three dimensions, “Revenue Model”, “Value Proposition”, and “Value Creation Process”, are reorganized to form the horizontal axis. This matrix can now be used to map the important factors identified in the previous section regarding the origin of the data, its path to the recipient and the revenue flow to be realised:

	Data(flow)	External business model	Internal business modell	cash(flow)
I2I	Manage / prepare data	Prepare ext. business model	Prepare int. Business model	Cost saving
I2E	Publish data	Support ext. Business model	Offer new business model	Purchasing services
E2I	Record data	Use ext. Business model	Substitute / expand int. Business model	Sell services
E2E	External data circulation	External business model circulation	Outsource internal business model	Growth of competitors

Figure 1: Monetisation Pathway Matrix

The matrix records the target customer dimension alongside internal and external factors. Internal factors impact the company itself, while external factors originate outside the company and influence it indirectly. The sub-dimensions “Internal to Internal” (I2I), “Internal to External” (I2E), “External to Internal” (E2I), and “External to External” (E2E) capture all influence combinations. I2I, where value creation remains fully internal, is ideal. In contrast, E2E, involving no company input, is generally undesirable as it risks promoting competitors, except in specific cases discussed later. Between these extremes are publication (I2E) and internalisation (E2I). For sustainable models, the publication (I2E) is often preferable to internalisation (E2I).

The remaining dimensions are recorded horizontally. These are “Data (flow)”, “External business models”, “Internal business models”, and “Revenue (flow)”. This sequence can be understood as a process in which a data flow should generate a revenue flow through a business model. This is consistent with the dimensions of the Gassmann model: Value proposition, value creation process and revenue model. The characteristics of internal or external business models describe whether an independent business model is sought or whether external companies are to be supported. Thus, the matrix expands to 4x4 size and offers a total of 16 dimensions, as shown in Figure 1.

Each dimension describes a possible aspect of successful data monetisation. The matrix is intended to illustrate a path that can be understood both as a process chain and as a chronological sequence. It therefore aims to clarify your wishes and ideas regarding the data monetisation process. The matrix is also intended to encourage people to explore the other dimensions and thus identify alternative processes. The matrix aims to build up an initial understanding of the expected processes and to define the given boundary conditions.

The 16 dimensions are filled in and colour-coded. The colour coding was developed based on the analysis of data monetisation strategies and subsequently validated with the DATAMITE pilots to ensure practical applicability and relevance. Green areas represent preferred dimensions that every user should strive for. Yellow areas are indifferent: no clear advantages or disadvantages are to be expected here, or these are situation-dependent. Red areas should be avoided.

Internal process steps (I2I) should always be preferred. This means that a company should ideally process its internal data. As part of the business model, it may be an objective to support external companies in their projects. This is mapped in the matrix using a process that includes the dimensions of internal and external business models. The exact opposite can be the case if another of the company's business models is supported by its data (internal business model). Ultimately, it is also possible to save costs or increase process efficiency with data.

If the company interacts directly with external partners, these actions are recorded in the I2E line. Data can be made available here to exchange it for another good, e.g. money. A company can also support other companies directly with data or enter the market with its business model. However, a flow of revenue from internal to external should be carefully managed to avoid unnecessary financial outflows and resource inefficiencies. This aligns with principles from cost management theories (Kaplan & Cooper, 1998) and the resource-based view of the firm (Barney, 1991), which emphasise the importance of optimising internal resources and minimising external dependencies to maintain competitiveness and profitability.

The dimensions in the E2I series, i.e. from external to internal, are usually coloured yellow and should therefore be understood as indifferent. When data comes into the company from external sources, services are used (external business model), or even internal business models are expanded by external services (internal business model substitute/expand), and the company becomes dependent. This dependency may be tolerable at first but should not become a threat to the company's existence in the long term. Only the flow of sales from external to internal is seen as positive, as it can increase the company's sales.

The External to External (E2E) dimension should be avoided, as it excludes company involvement and can strengthen competitors. Additionally, outsourcing internal models should be avoided, as it creates dependencies. Moreover, your efforts should not lead to an external data cycle: This creates more data on the market that the company cannot use. The external business models of other companies may be strengthened and grow (external business model circulates). In the long term, this carries the risk that your business models will be replaced by other companies.

This matrix outlines potential actions for developing a data monetisation strategy, especially useful for creating a new business model. Initially appealing options, like supporting the expansion of an external company’s model, may later result in dependencies or substitution. This could enable competitors to replicate and outperform the company’s model, reducing revenue. The goal of the Monetisation Matrix is to progress from the left to the right, with steps shown by blue squares and the starting point highlighted in red/pink, as you can see in the example in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Data-as-a-Service Pathway

4.2.2 Questionnaire for the Data Monetisation Framework

Independently of the matrix presented, another model has been created. This has the form of a questionnaire and is explained in this subsection (Table 2). During the literature review, it was found that there are not only four main strategies with multiple sub-strategies but that the strategies can generally be grouped according to complexity and target group. These different elements are addressed in the framework in the form of a questionnaire with defined answer options. The questions are intended to shed light on different aspects of data monetisation as well

as the motivation and capabilities of the company. There are four answer options for each question, each of which ranges in terms of content from "easy" and "simple" to "complex" and "extensive". The aim is that the target group and complexity are not apparent. This is achieved by the following measures: 1. The questions are asked openly; there are no specifications in terms of industry, company size or target group. This has the advantage that the lack of industry consideration discussed in the previous chapters is considered. This means that all companies of all sizes are addressed. 2. All answer options follow the pattern of increasing complexity. For this purpose, the answers are additionally numbered. 3. The addressee aspect is addressed in several questions. These questions are distributed regularly throughout the questionnaire and not directly one after the other. 4. Cumulative answers will be related. This means that the answers expand multiple options, which is particularly important for cumulative considerations. These answers do not stand alone but rather build upon previous ones, thereby expanding the scope of analysis and enabling a more nuanced understanding of the respondent's strategy. For instance, in the questionnaire, answers marked with an asterisk (*) indicate an extension of prior options. As seen in the framework, responses such as "*controlling*" or "*market data*" under the question "Which internal departments do I involve?" go beyond basic answers to include broader, interconnected considerations. The cumulative structure ensures that respondents can progressively refine their answers, reflecting the complexity of real-world data monetisation scenarios. Such marked responses also highlight dependencies or enhancements that expand strategic decision-making beyond isolated answers. This results in the following 13 questions with their possible answers:

QUESTIONS	ANSWERS			
	For each question, one of four possible answers must be selected. Options starting with * are to be considered cumulative to the answer above them.			
Who is my customer?	1. Lower Management	2. Middle Management	3./4. Upper Management	3./4. Upper Management
What do I offer?	1. Data	2. (Processed) Data / Analyses	3. Analyses	4. Digital Product
How do I obtain my data?	1. Utilize existing data	2. Targeted production & customized analysis	3. Process / analyse data	4. Conceptualize / develop new GM / services (using data as a means to an end)
Which analysis methods can I use?	1. Experts, industry knowledge	2. *In-depth knowledge of the own company, Deep Learning	3. *Market Data Analytics or ability to track / analyse own sales	4. *Executive Management Model Development
Which internal departments do I involve?	1. Legal department, GDPR officer, data producers, sales (& marketing), IT department	2. *Controlling, department	3. *Controlling (pricing and pricing model), sales	4. *Executive Management
Which external departments do I address? Or: Whom do I need to convince?	1. Subsidiaries, R&D, IT	2. Controlling	3. Decision-makers at (main) departmental level	4. *Executive Management Level
How is the distribution done?	1. No specific target audience addressed, make accessible to a broad audience, Google Ads	2. *Blog posts, explanatory videos	3. *Trade journals	4. *Trade fair
What value should be created?	1. Prestige / Reputation / Value creation through third parties (advertising/data sales); Lock-In Effect	2. *Reduce internal costs / increase efficiency	3. *Monetisation through sales	4. *New services -> New GM -> New markets -> Further revenue. Differentiation from competition.
Special requirements	1. Data security, data backup, platform for processing and providing data, quality control, continuity management	2. *Analytical skills to identify own weaknesses & address them (know-how and (prevention) will)	3. *Billing infrastructure, market survey?	4. *Innovation scouting, agile project management, venture capital, visions
Should my offer be modifiable (possibly caused by external factors)?	1. Very high flexibility	2. High flexibility	3. Low flexibility	4. Little flexibility
What resources are needed?	1. IT, labour	2. *Computing power	3. *Cross-departmental communication, market data	4. *Insights into company philosophy, company strategy
Which customer problems should be solved?	1. Problems the customer is not aware of; "nice-to-have," one can manage without help	2. *Efficiency improvement	3. *Larger problems of customers willing to pay for them; problems threatening the customer's existence	4. *Problems affecting the customer's transformation
What type of monetisation do I want to pursue?	1. None - the data is shared for free	2. Cost savings are the goal.	3. A (one-time) cash flow is intended to be generated.	4. A recurring cash flow is intended to be generated.
Summary	1. "Identify that your own data has value."	2. "Recognize that (my) data helps"	3. "Make data attractive"	4. "Pave new ways"

Table 2: Questionnaire for the Data Monetisation Framework

4.2.3 Strategy Profiles for Data Monetisation

Figure 3 displays the different strategy profiles identified through the literature review, the ecosystem analysis and the pilot interviews on data monetisation. The framework structures them according to internal and external monetisation strategies. Moreover, it differentiates the external data monetisation strategies between direct, indirect, and non-monetary strategies. Task 4.4 can build on this framework, allowing the addition of further strategies under the non-monetary category as the project progresses. These strategy profiles make a crucial point in orienting customers and helping them with their data monetisation capabilities. The following 12 strategies for data monetisation have been identified and will be analysed using the 4x4 pathway matrix, with the corresponding questionnaire answers for each strategy provided in Appendix B: Strategy Questionnaire Responses

1. Data-as-a-service
2. Information-as-a-service
3. Answers-as-a-service
4. Reduce costs
5. Data Network
6. Wrapping
7. Servitisation
8. New Products / Services
9. Data Bartering
10. Share-for-free
11. Data Platform Providing
12. Data Platform Refining

Figure 3: Monetisation Strategy Overview

1. Data-as-a-service

Data-as-a-service (DaaS) is a prominent data-driven business model where a central organisation, often via a digital platform like Facebook or LinkedIn, gathers and offers anonymised raw data for commercial purposes through a marketplace. Users, such as developers or solution providers, utilise these datasets to enhance their offerings or explore new market opportunities. Successful implementation requires robust data collection capabilities, a trusted platform, and effective anonymisation procedures. Revenue is typically generated through pay-per-data or subscription models. While attractive for companies with significant data volume and market dominance, only a few, like Amazon and Google, have managed to profitably sustain this model, with many past attempts by others failing (Stechow, Schäfer, & Brugger, 2022).

Figure 4 illustrates the pathway followed by the DaaS strategy, highlighting the data flow from internal to external (I2E) sources as company data is sold directly. This movement of data generates revenue, resulting in a cash flow from external sources back into the company (E2I).

Figure 4: Data-as-a-Service Pathway

2. Information-as-a-service

The Information-as-a-service (IaaS) business model centres on providing analyses or reports rather than raw data. These analyses are customized to meet specific customer needs and can be derived from either internally collected data pools, augmenting the Data-as-a-Service (DaaS) model, or external data sources. A diverse range of customers, from businesses to end consumers, can benefit from these insights, primarily aimed at making informed decisions. Successful implementation requires not only raw data but also analytical and visualization capabilities, coupled with industry expertise. Revenue generation within the IaaS model typically mirrors that of DaaS, encompassing sales of individual analyses or subscription-based access. Costs primarily stem from data acquisition, processing, and analysis creation, yet structured analyses often command higher prices due to their depth and specificity. IaaS models are particularly appealing to companies with robust analytical capabilities or those seeking to develop them strategically (Stechow, Schäfer, & Brugger, 2022).

Figure 5 depicts the pathway for the IaaS strategy, illustrating how internal data is utilized to generate insights and create valuable information (I2I) that is attractive to customers. This data is then shared with external customers (I2E). The sharing of the information subsequently leads to a cash flow from customers who pay for the information back to the company (E2I).

Figure 5: Information-as-a-Service Pathway

3. Answers-as-a-service

Answers-as-a-service (AaaS) provides direct responses to user queries, enhancing decision-making. It often generates additional revenue streams through consulting or support services, appealing to both consumers and businesses in need of tailored guidance. Companies offering AaaS require not only data but also a profound understanding of user needs and market dynamics. Trust in data provision is essential for its success, while revenue models typically involve pay-per-answer or subscriptions, with higher prices for tailored responses. AaaS suits companies with strong customer relationships and industry knowledge. Challenges include identifying critical questions and determining the value of provided answers, but scalability and additional revenue opportunities through consulting or support services enhance its appeal (Stechow, Schäfer, & Brugger, 2022).

Figure 6 illustrates the pathway for the AaaS strategy, demonstrating that the service provider

Figure 6: Answers-as-a-Service Pathway

first receives external client data (E2I). Then this external data is used to generate insights and create valuable information. This gathered information is then utilized internally (I2I) to develop solutions tailored to external business models. The sale of those solutions ultimately generates revenue, resulting in a cash flow from external sources back into the company (E2I).

4. Reduce Cost

By employing criteria-based data valuation, companies can identify valuable datasets and optimise their utilisation. This involves assessing factors like data quality, relevance, and timeliness, allowing for informed decision-making regarding data acquisition and storage. Cost-based data valuation further enhances understanding by quantifying data-related expenses, including collection, storage, preprocessing, and maintenance costs. Through this, companies can allocate resources more efficiently and plan for future data monetisation opportunities. Reporting-based data valuation extends this by integrating data reporting into annual financial statements, akin to sustainability reporting. Finally, transaction-based data valuation enables direct data monetisation through sales or marketplace trading, leveraging new business models like as-a-service or subscription-based models (Stein, Holst, Stich, & Maass, 2021).

Figure 7 outlines the pathway for the cost reduction strategy, showing how data is used internally (I2I) to identify hidden potentials for cost reductions. Based on those potentials, business plans aimed at achieving cost savings can be developed internally (I2I). Ultimately, the business model generates an internal (I2I) cash flow by reducing costs based on the identified potentials.

Figure 7: Reduce-cost Pathway

5. Data Network

In data-driven business models, a robust data network facilitates collaboration among market players, driving value creation for companies. It involves integrating internal databases to break down silos and streamline data access across departments. Additionally, integration with suppliers enhances supply chain coordination and efficiency through technologies like electronic data interchange. Customer integration is crucial, with active participation in value creation through data provision. Partnerships with market counterparts of equal or superior value extend collaboration beyond data integration, fostering long-term cooperation for joint value creation and innovation (Woroch & Strobel, 2022).

Figure 8 depicts the pathway for the data network strategy, where internal data is structured (I2I) and then published to external parties (I2E). This can facilitate the integration of external parties into the business model (I2I). This approach enhances collaboration and connectivity, strengthening the company's network and strategic partnerships.

Figure 8: Data Network Pathway

6. Wrapping

In the context of data monetisation, "wrapping" refers to the practice of enhancing core products or services by incorporating additional information or data-related features. This involves providing supplementary information or insights that add value to the core offering and make it more appealing to customers. For example, United Parcel Service (UPS) enhances its package delivery service by providing detailed information about the package's journey, delivery status, estimated arrival time, and other relevant data points. By offering this additional information, UPS not only improves the customer experience but also adds value to its core delivery service. Similarly, in other industries such as retail, wrapping can involve providing customers with additional data or insights related to the products or services they purchase. For instance, retailers may offer demographic sales reports, industry benchmark metrics, or analytics software to help customers optimise their marketing, pricing, or distribution strategies (Woerner & Wixom, 2015).

Figure 9 illustrates the pathway for the wrapping strategy, where data is first internally prepared (I2I) by the company. This data is then used to develop a business model for external use (I2I). This model enables the sale of products or services based on the new business plan, with the data flow remaining internal. Revenue is generated through a cash flow from external sources back into the company (E2I).

Figure 9: Wrapping Pathway

7. Servitisation

Servitisation is essential in data-driven business models, enhancing value creation and revenue generation by integrating services into traditional product offerings. This shift to a product-service hybrid model allows manufacturers to leverage service-generated data, enabling insights that optimise operations, improve decision-making, and increase profitability (Opresnik & Taisch, 2015; Woerner & Wixom, 2015).

Unlike Information-as-a-Service, which focuses on standalone analytical insights, Servitization integrates data-driven services with physical products, creating hybrid offerings that enhance product value, foster customer loyalty, and drive recurring revenue.

A practical example is the Equipment-as-a-Service (EaaS) model used by Heidelberg Druckmaschinen, where customers subscribe to a service that includes machine usage, maintenance, and real-time performance optimisation. This ensures uptime for customers and generates continuous revenue for the provider. Such industrial subscription models illustrate the potential of Servitisation to transform traditional industries into service-oriented ecosystems.

Figure 10 outlines the pathway for the Servitisation strategy, where data is prepared internally (I2I) by the company to develop a business model for external use (I2I). This model enables the sale of integrated product-service offerings based on the new business plan, with the data flow remaining internal as it supports the delivery of services alongside traditional products. Revenue is generated through a cash flow from external sources back into the company (E2I).

Figure 10: Servitization Pathway

8. New Products / Services

Companies often employ a strategy of creating entirely new offerings for customers based on data insights. These offerings may include new products and services that are either fuelled by data or entirely devised from insights gleaned from data analysis. For example, IBM developed a service centred around sensors installed in the homes of elderly individuals to monitor vital signs and daily activities. By leveraging this data, anomalies can be identified, and relevant services can be alerted, leading to potential cost savings of up to 30 per cent. Other companies utilize data to innovate services that complement their core offerings, as seen with Netflix and DHL. This approach is particularly evident in industries like product maintenance, with companies such as Siemens, Thyssenkrupp, and Pirelli. The economic benefits of this strategy include the creation of new revenue streams and the exploration of new business segments (Baecker, Engert, Pfaff, & Krcmar, 2020).

Figure 11 illustrates the pathway for the new products/services strategy, where data is also first prepared internally by the company (I2I). This data is again used to develop a business model for external use (I2I). This model supports the creation and sale of new products or services, with the data flow remaining internal to drive the development of these offerings. Revenue is generated through a cash flow from external sources back into the company (E2I).

Figure 11: New Products / Services Pathway

9. Data Bartering

Data bartering involves companies exchanging data for valuable assets, such as other data, insights, tools, or services. For instance, data and analytics providers may offer discounts based on contributions to their database, or directly exchange data with business partners, particularly in finance. In the retail industry, data bartering often involves trading point-of-sale data for demographic information or analytics software. The economic benefits of data bartering include the exchanged value in the form of tools, services, or data (Baecker, Engert, Pfaff, & Krcmar, 2020).

Figure 12 depicts the pathway for the data bartering strategy, where data is prepared for external use (I2E) to support external business models (I2E). This creates the potential for a second data flow directed back to the company (E2I), resulting in a mutually beneficial data exchange.

Figure 12: Data Bartering Pathway

10. Share-for-free

A strategy to attract users and build a community is offering services free of charge, sometimes referred to as a freemium model. In this model, businesses provide basic data or services for free to encourage user engagement, while charging a premium for access to more detailed or advanced features. Popular examples include music and movie streaming platforms like YouTube, Spotify, Alexa, and Hulu Music, which offer a wide range of content to attract a large user base while reserving certain features or content for premium subscribers. Free content can add value by driving more traffic to the product or service enabling extensive data generation of users and thus gaining a competitive advantage e.g. for non-free products or services (Ofulue & Benyoucef, 2022).

Figure 13 outlines the pathway for the share-for-free strategy, where data is prepared internally for external use (I2E), supporting existing external business models (I2E). Once exposed to numerous external users, this data can circulate across different external business models (E2E). As a result, information about the usage of this data can be gathered and leveraged to expand the company’s business model (E2I).

Figure 13: Share-for-free Pathway

11. Data Platform Providing

The platform provider facilitates the matching of supply and demand in manufacturing through transaction and innovation platforms. Transaction platforms connect buyers and sellers, exemplified by Airbnb and Tapio. Innovation platforms, like Microsoft Azure, provide tools for customers to develop innovations. Platform operators offer standardized services while customers provide customized services to their end users. Success hinges on achieving critical mass, either through direct platform users or individual customers. Revenue primarily comes from transaction costs paid by platform users, but platform operators may also trade their data or services. Consortia among competitors are common, pooling assets to achieve necessary data density. Platforms targeting individual customers show promise due to their alignment with existing products and established customer bases (Trauth, Bergs, & Prinz, 2021).

Figure 14 illustrates the pathway for the data platform operator strategy, where external data is collected (E2I) on a data platform to create a circulation of external business models (E2E). This service of providing a platform generates revenue through transactional costs, generating a cash flow from external users to the platform operator (E2I).

Figure 14: Data Platform Providing Pathway

12. Data Platform Refining

The platform refiner, a derivative of the platform provider, utilizes data and transaction insights from its platform to create added value for its customers. While it shares similarities with the Platform Operator, the Enhancer's services are more tailored to individual customer needs, requiring the same level of data density. The value provided depends on the accessibility of data. Typically, greater access to customer processes and products necessitates a higher level of trust to access the data. In practice, manufacturing companies in the B2B sector often allow only selective data access, with data ownership remaining with the customer. These services include pre-built analysis tools for data and text mining, or pre-trained neural networks for video and image analysis (Trauth, Bergs, & Prinz, 2021).

Figure 15 depicts the pathway for the data platform refiner strategy, where external data, generated from operating the data exchange platform, is collected (E2I) and then refined internally (I2I). The refined results form a more complex product specifically targeted at the needs of the platform users, which is made available for external circulation (E2E). This service is then sold through transactional costs, generating revenue from external users to the platform refiner (E2I).

Figure 15: Data Platform Refining Pathway

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, Task 4.1 of the DATAMITE project has successfully established a strategic foundation for enhancing data monetisation. Through pilot interviews and a comprehensive ecosystem analysis that examined stakeholders, value chains, value propositions, and revenue mechanisms, we developed tailored strategy profiles that address both internal and external monetisation approaches.

The application of the Value Proposition Canvas has allowed us to structure the development of our framework and transform our findings into practical profiles that organisations can utilise to optimise their data assets. Additionally, the creation of a user-friendly questionnaire will enable DATAMITE users to receive personalised recommendations, guiding them toward the most suitable monetisation strategies for their specific contexts.

Looking ahead, the insights from Task 4.1 will be operationalised in Tasks 4.2 and 4.3. Task 4.2 will focus on defining key performance indicators (KPIs) for the fair valuation of datasets and establishing mechanisms for their computation. Meanwhile, Task 4.3 will explore data from an economic perspective, developing business cases and models for data-sharing platforms. This integration of findings will ensure coherence across the project and facilitate the effective implementation of data monetisation strategies.

By operationalising these strategies, we aim to empower organisations to navigate the complexities of data monetisation, optimise their data assets, and create sustainable revenue streams. The groundwork laid in Task 4.1 is just the beginning, and we are eager to see how these strategies will evolve and be applied in the subsequent phases of the DATAMITE project, ultimately contributing to a robust ecosystem for data monetisation in Europe.

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Appendix A: Guidelines of the Monetisation Framework

This section provides a step-by-step guide for using the data monetisation framework to help users select appropriate data monetisation strategies. The framework is implemented as a web application and utilises two key tools:

1. A **4x4 Pathway Matrix** to evaluate the company's current or desired future data monetisation status.
2. A **Questionnaire** to assess the business's strategic profile and further refine monetisation strategies.

Both tools work together to automatically interpret and provide actionable results based on the user's inputs, guiding them toward the best data monetisation strategy.

Part 1: Pathway Matrix

Goal: The 4x4 Pathway Matrix is designed to provide a comprehensive overview of the current status of your company's data monetisation strategy. It helps visualise how your data flows through internal and external business processes and highlights possible monetisation opportunities or risks. Specifically, it helps map key factors regarding the origin of the data, its path to the recipient, and the revenue flow that needs to be realised.

Matrix Inputs:

- **Data Source:** Information on where the data comes from (internal or external).
- **Business Models:** Whether the data is used for internal purposes or shared externally.

Matrix Outputs:

- Automatic interpretation of the results to highlight the best strategy for your company based on internal and external factors. Specifically, the output is a **colour-coded guide** that indicates preferred, indifferent, or avoidable pathways for data monetisation.

Step-by-Step Guide for Using the Pathway Matrix

Step 1: Navigation

Visit the DATA monetisation framework and navigate to the matrix.

Step 2: Identify Data Sources and Data Flow

Start by mapping out where your data comes from. Is it generated internally within the company, or is it sourced externally (e.g., from partners or third parties)? Then, decide on how your data moves through and outside the company. To answer these questions, the multiple-choice answers are provided:

- **Internal to Internal (I2I):** Data is sourced and used internally to improve processes or create new products/services.
- **Internal to External (I2E):** Data is sourced internally, but it is shared and processed externally by external partners for mutual benefit.
- **External to Internal (E2I):** Data is sourced externally, but they are processed completely internally to improve processes or create new products/services.
- **External to External (E2E):** Is it sourced and used completely externally without any influence from the company?

Step 3: Decide on Data Flow that Should Generate Revenue

Decide if the data is used to support your internal business model (e.g., improving processes, launching new products) or if it's shared with external businesses to support their objectives. In this step, you can choose one or more of the following: Data (flow), External business models, Internal business models, and Revenue (flow).

Step 4: Track Revenue Flow

Step 5: Matrix Results

Once the matrix is completed, the platform will automatically analyse the selected dimensions and provide the following:

- The **ideal data flow** for your company (indicated in green).
- **Neutral** or context-dependent actions (indicated in yellow).
- **Risky actions** that should be avoided (indicated in red).

The system will suggest the most efficient and profitable pathways to maximise data value while minimising risks, such as inadvertently supporting competitors. The result can help in understanding how the data ultimately generates revenue. For example, does it result in cost savings, selling services or products, and supporting competitors or external businesses?

Part 2: Questionnaire

Goal: The questionnaire complements the matrix by exploring various strategic aspects of your company's data monetisation. It helps refine and detail the company's strategic profile, complexity, and monetisation potential.

Questionnaire Inputs:

The questionnaire asks a series of strategic questions about your business, including:

- **Who is your customer?**
- **What do you offer?**
- **How do you obtain your data?**
- **What type of monetisation do you pursue?**

Each question has four answer options that range in complexity, from simple strategies to more complex and sophisticated ones. The answers are cumulative and will expand based on the complexity level chosen.

Questionnaire Outputs:

- Automatic **interpretation of results**, so you don't need to analyse the questionnaire manually. The framework will provide a recommendation on the best data monetisation strategy tailored to your specific business model based on your answers.

Step-by-Step Guide for Using the Questionnaire

Step 1: Navigation

Visit the DATA monetisation framework and navigate to the questionnaire.

Step 2: Answer Questions

For each question, select the answer that best describes your company's current situation or the goals you wish to achieve. Each answer comes with four options, ranging from simple to complex. Start by choosing answers that reflect the current level of complexity in your business model. Some answers are cumulative, meaning you may need to select options that build upon each other. Some questions will be asked about special business conditions, such as:

- Whether your business model is modifiable based on external factors.
- Specific customer problems you aim to solve with data.

Step 3: Submit Answers & Receive Results

Once you have completed the questionnaire, and submitted your answers, the framework will automatically interpret your answers and:

- Provide **tailored recommendations** for the best suitable data monetisation strategy that aligns with your strategic profile and your business's needs.

Appendix B: Strategy Questionnaire Responses

QUESTIONS Data-as-a-Service	ANSWERS For each question, one of four possible answers must be selected. Options starting with * are to be considered cumulative to the answer above them.	Visualization of Questionnaire			
Who is my customer?	2. Middle Management				
What do I offer?	1. Data				
How do I obtain my data?	1. Utilize existing data				
Which analysis methods can I use?	1. Experts, industry knowledge				
Which internal departments do I involve?	2. Controlling, department				
Which external departments do I address? Or: Whom do I need to convince?	3. Decision-makers at (main) departmental level				
How is the distribution done?	3. *Trade journals				
What value should be created?	3. *Monetisation through sales				
Special requirements	1. Data security, data backup, platform for processing and providing data, quality control, continuity management				
Should my offer be modifiable (possibly caused by external factors)?	1. Very high flexibility				
What resources are needed?	2. *Computing power				
Which customer problems should be solved?	2. *Efficiency improvement				
What type of monetisation do I want to pursue?	3. A (one-time) cash flow is intended to be generated.				
Summary	2. "Recognize that (my) data helps"				

Table 3: Data-as-a-Service Questionnaire

QUESTIONS Information-as-a-Service	ANSWERS For each question, one of four possible answers must be selected. Options starting with * are to be considered cumulative to the answer above them.	Visualization of Questionnaire			
Who is my customer?	2. Middle Management				
What do I offer?	3. Analyses				
How do I obtain my data?	2. Targeted production & customized analysis				
Which analysis methods can I use?	3. *Market Data Analytics or ability to track/analyse own sales				
Which internal departments do I involve?	3. *Controlling (pricing and pricing model), sales				
Which external departments do I address? Or: Whom do I need to convince?	3. Decision-makers at (main) departmental level				
How is the distribution done?	3. *Trade journals				
What value should be created?	3. *Monetisation through sales				
Special requirements	2. *Analytical skills to identify own weaknesses & address them (know-how and (prevention) will)				
Should my offer be modifiable (possibly caused by external factors)?	2. High flexibility				
What resources are needed?	3. *Cross-departmental communication, market data				
Which customer problems should be solved?	2. *Efficiency improvement				
What type of monetisation do I want to pursue?	3. A (one-time) cash flow is intended to be generated.				
Summary	3. "Make data attractive"				

Table 4: Information-as-a-Service Questionnaire

QUESTIONS Answers-as-a-Service	ANSWERS For each question, one of four possible answers must be selected. Options starting with * are to be considered cumulative to the answer above them.	Visualization of Questionnaire			
Who is my customer?	2. Middle Management				
What do I offer?	1. Data				
How do I obtain my data?	1. Utilize existing data				
Which analysis methods can I use?	3. *Market Data Analytics or ability to track/analyse own sales				
Which internal departments do I involve?	2. *Controlling, department				
Which external departments do I address? Or: Whom do I need to convince?	1. Subsidiaries, R&D, IT				
How is the distribution done?	1. No specific target audience addressed, make accessible to a broad audience, Google Ads				
What value should be created?	2. *Reduce internal costs / increase efficiency				
Special requirements	2. *Analytical skills to identify own weaknesses & address them (know-how and (prevention) will)				
Should my offer be modifiable (possibly caused by external factors)?	4. Little flexibility				
What resources are needed?	3. *Cross-departmental communication, market data				
Which customer problems should be solved?	2. *Efficiency improvement				
What type of monetisation do I want to pursue?	2. Cost savings are the goal.				
Summary	2. "Recognize that (my) data helps"				

Table 5: Answers-as-a-Service Questionnaire

QUESTIONS Reduce Cost	ANSWERS For each question, one of four possible answers must be selected. Options starting with * are to be considered cumulative to the answer above them.	Visualization of Questionnaire			
Who is my customer?	2. Middle Management				
What do I offer?	1. Data				
How do I obtain my data?	1. Utilize existing data				
Which analysis methods can I use?	3. *Market Data Analytics or ability to track/analyse own sales				
Which internal departments do I involve?	2. *Controlling, department				
Which external departments do I address? Or: Whom do I need to convince?	1. Subsidiaries, R&D, IT				
How is the distribution done?	1. No specific target audience addressed, make accessible to a broad audience, Google Ads				
What value should be created?	2. *Reduce internal costs / increase efficiency				
Special requirements	2. *Analytical skills to identify own weaknesses & address them (know-how and (prevention) will)				
Should my offer be modifiable (possibly caused by external factors)?	4. Little flexibility				
What resources are needed?	3. *Cross-departmental communication, market data				
Which customer problems should be solved?	2. *Efficiency improvement				
What type of monetisation do I want to pursue?	2. Cost savings are the goal.				
Summary	2. "Recognize that (my) data helps"				

Table 6: Reduce-Cost Questionnaire

QUESTIONS Data Network	ANSWERS For each question, one of four possible answers must be selected. Options starting with * are to be considered cumulative to the answer above them.	Visualization of Questionnaire			
Who is my customer?	2. Middle Management				
What do I offer?	1. Data				
How do I obtain my data?	1. Utilize existing data				
Which analysis methods can I use?	2. *In-depth knowledge of the own company, Deep Learning				
Which internal departments do I involve?	2. *Controlling, department				
Which external departments do I address? Or: Whom do I need to convince?	2. Controlling				
How is the distribution done?	1. No specific target audience addressed, make accessible to a broad audience, Google Ads				
What value should be created?	2. *Reduce internal costs / increase efficiency				
Special requirements	2. *Analytical skills to identify own weaknesses & address them (know-how and (prevention) will)				
Should my offer be modifiable (possibly caused by external factors)?	2. High flexibility				
What resources are needed?	2. *Computing power				
Which customer problems should be solved?	2. *Efficiency improvement				
What type of monetisation do I want to pursue?	2. Cost savings are the goal.				
Summary	2. "Recognize that (my) data helps"				

Table 7: Data Network Questionnaire

QUESTIONS Data Wrapping	ANSWERS For each question, one of four possible answers must be selected. Options starting with * are to be considered cumulative to the answer above them.	Visualization of Questionnaire			
Who is my customer?	3./4. Upper Management				
What do I offer?	2. (Processed) Data / Analyses				
How do I obtain my data?	2. Targeted production & customized analysis				
Which analysis methods can I use?	3. *Market Data Analytics or ability to track/analyse own sales				
Which internal departments do I involve?	4. *Executive Management				
Which external departments do I address? Or: Whom do I need to convince?	3. Decision-makers at (main) departmental level				
How is the distribution done?	2. *Blog posts, explanatory videos				
What value should be created?	2. *Reduce internal costs / increase efficiency				
Special requirements	3. *Billing infrastructure, market survey?				
Should my offer be modifiable (possibly caused by external factors)?	3. Low flexibility				
What resources are needed?	3. *Cross-departmental communication, market data				
Which customer problems should be solved?	2. *Efficiency improvement				
What type of monetisation do I want to pursue?	2. Cost savings are the goal.				
Summary	2. "Recognize that (my) data helps"				

Table 8: Wrapping Questionnaire

QUESTIONS Servitization	ANSWERS For each question, one of four possible answers must be selected. Options starting with * are to be considered cumulative to the answer above them.	Visualization of Questionnaire			
Who is my customer?	3./4. Upper Management				
What do I offer?	4. Digital Product				
How do I obtain my data?	4. Conceptualize/develop new GM/services (using data as a means to an end)				
Which analysis methods can I use?	4. *Executive Management Model Development				
Which internal departments do I involve?	4. *Executive Management				
Which external departments do I address? Or: Whom do I need to convince?	3. Decision-makers at (main) departmental level				
How is the distribution done?	4. *Trade fair				
What value should be created?	4. *New services -> New GM -> New markets -> Further revenue. Differentiation from competition.				
Special requirements	4. *Innovation scouting, agile project management, venture capital, visions				
Should my offer be modifiable (possibly caused by external factors)?	4. Little flexibility				
What resources are needed?	4. *Insights into company philosophy, company strategy				
Which customer problems should be solved?	3. *Larger problems of customers willing to pay for them; problems threatening the customer's existence				
What type of monetisation do I want to pursue?	4. A recurring cash flow is intended to be generated.				
Summary	4. "Pave new ways"				

Table 9: Servitization Questionnaire

QUESTIONS New Products / Services	ANSWERS For each question, one of four possible answers must be selected. Options starting with * are to be considered cumulative to the answer above them.	Visualization of Questionnaire			
Who is my customer?	3./4. Upper Management				
What do I offer?	4. Digital Product				
How do I obtain my data?	4. Conceptualize/develop new GM/services (using data as a means to an end)				
Which analysis methods can I use?	4. *Executive Management Model Development				
Which internal departments do I involve?	4. *Executive Management				
Which external departments do I address? Or: Whom do I need to convince?	3. Decision-makers at (main) departmental level				
How is the distribution done?	4. *Trade fair				
What value should be created?	4. *New services -> New GM -> New markets -> Further revenue. Differentiation from competition.				
Special requirements	4. *Innovation scouting, agile project management, venture capital, visions				
Should my offer be modifiable (possibly caused by external factors)?	4. Little flexibility				
What resources are needed?	4. *Insights into company philosophy, company strategy				
Which customer problems should be solved?	4. *Problems affecting the customer's transformation				
What type of monetisation do I want to pursue?	4. A recurring cash flow is intended to be generated.				
Summary	4. "Pave new ways"				

Table 10: New Products / Services Questionnaire

QUESTIONS Data Bartering	ANSWERS For each question, one of four possible answers must be selected. Options starting with * are to be considered cumulative to the answer above them.	Visualization of Questionnaire			
Who is my customer?	2. Middle Management				
What do I offer?	1. Data				
How do I obtain my data?	2. Targeted production & customized analysis				
Which analysis methods can I use?	2. *In-depth knowledge of the own company, Deep Learning				
Which internal departments do I involve?	1. Legal department, GDPR officer, data producers, sales (& marketing), IT department				
Which external departments do I address? Or: Whom do I need to convince?	1. Subsidiaries, R&D, IT				
How is the distribution done?	1. No specific target audience addressed, make accessible to a broad audience, Google Ads				
What value should be created?	1. Prestige / Reputation / Value creation through third parties (advertising/data sales); Lock-In Effect				
Special requirements	1. Data security, data backup, platform for processing and providing data, quality control, continuity management				
Should my offer be modifiable (possibly caused by external factors)?	1. Very high flexibility				
What resources are needed?	2. *Computing power				
Which customer problems should be solved?	1. Problems the customer is not aware of; "nice-to-have," one can manage without help				
What type of monetisation do I want to pursue?	1. None - the data is shared for free				
Summary	1. "Identify that your own data has value."				

Table 11: Data Bartering Questionnaire

QUESTIONS Share for free	ANSWERS For each question, one of four possible answers must be selected. Options starting with * are to be considered cumulative to the answer above them.	Visualization of Questionnaire			
Who is my customer?	2. Middle Management				
What do I offer?	1. Data				
How do I obtain my data?	1. Utilize existing data				
Which analysis methods can I use?	1. Experts, industry knowledge				
Which internal departments do I involve?	2. *Controlling, department				
Which external departments do I address? Or: Whom do I need to convince?	3. Decision-makers at (main) departmental level				
How is the distribution done?	2. *Blog posts, explanatory videos				
What value should be created?	1. Prestige / Reputation / Value creation through third parties (advertising/data sales); Lock-In Effect				
Special requirements	1. Data security, data backup, platform for processing and providing data, quality control, continuity management				
Should my offer be modifiable (possibly caused by external factors)?	1. Very high flexibility				
What resources are needed?	2. *Computing power				
Which customer problems should be solved?	1. Problems the customer is not aware of; "nice-to-have," one can manage without help				
What type of monetisation do I want to pursue?	1. None - the data is shared for free				
Summary	1. "Identify that your own data has value."				

Table 12: Share for free Questionnaire

QUESTIONS Data Platform Operator	ANSWERS For each question, one of four possible answers must be selected. Options starting with * are to be considered cumulative to the answer above them.	Visualization of Questionnaire			
Who is my customer?	2. Middle Management				
What do I offer?	2. (Processed) Data / Analyses				
How do I obtain my data?	1. Utilize existing data				
Which analysis methods can I use?	1. Experts, industry knowledge				
Which internal departments do I involve?	2. *Controlling, department				
Which external departments do I address? Or: Whom do I need to convince?	2. Controlling				
How is the distribution done?	2. *Blog posts, explanatory videos				
What value should be created?	3. *Monetisation through sales				
Special requirements	3. *Billing infrastructure, market survey?				
Should my offer be modifiable (possibly caused by external factors)?	3. Low flexibility				
What resources are needed?	3. *Cross-departmental communication, market data				
Which customer problems should be solved?	3. *Larger problems of customers willing to pay for them; problems threatening the customer's existence				
What type of monetisation do I want to pursue?	3. A (one-time) cash flow is intended to be generated.				
Summary	2. "Recognize that (my) data helps"				

Table 13: Data Platform Operator Questionnaire

QUESTIONS Data Platform Refiner	ANSWERS For each question, one of four possible answers must be selected. Options starting with * are to be considered cumulative to the answer above them.	Visualization of Questionnaire			
Who is my customer?	2. Middle Management				
What do I offer?	3. Analyses				
How do I obtain my data?	2. Targeted production & customized analysis				
Which analysis methods can I use?	2. *In-depth knowledge of the own company, Deep Learning				
Which internal departments do I involve?	2. *Controlling, department				
Which external departments do I address? Or: Whom do I need to convince?	2. Controlling				
How is the distribution done?	2. *Blog posts, explanatory videos				
What value should be created?	3. *Monetisation through sales				
Special requirements	3. *Billing infrastructure, market survey?				
Should my offer be modifiable (possibly caused by external factors)?	1. Very high flexibility				
What resources are needed?	3. *Cross-departmental communication, market data				
Which customer problems should be solved?	3. *Larger problems of customers willing to pay for them; problems threatening the customer's existence				
What type of monetisation do I want to pursue?	3. A (one-time) cash flow is intended to be generated.				
Summary	3. "Make data attractive"				

Table 14: Data Platform Refiner Questionnaire